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Imported pottery from Urvinum Hortense: preliminary considerations

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Abstract: This paper aims to present a preliminary study of imported pottery from the site of Urvinum Hortense (Collemancio di Perugia, Italy). Waiting for more scientific data, this is the first attempt to date two specific archaeological contexts (the ancient baths and temple area) using foreign ceramic fragments.

Keywords: Urvinum Hortense, imported pottery, *Regio VI*.

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1. HISTOGRAPHIC AND GEOMORPHOLOGICAL INTRODUCTION TO THE CONTEXT.

The area of La Pieve in Collemancio (PG), where the roman municipium of Urvinum Hortense was built¹, is an extremely important archaeological site both for scientific research and for the opportunity of valorization of the territory².

Identified thanks to an inscription in 1864³, after numerous archaeological investigations in the early twentieth century, the site has very particular morpho-structural features, perched on the top of one of the highest hills of the Civitelle chain, which borders the right side of the northern Umbrian Valley⁴.

The hilly landform of the area provides the city with an open and yet protected location, as well as with water availability, as it can still be

¹ For references on Urvinum Hortense see MANCONI 1985; BINAZZI 1986; MATTEINI CHIARI 1992; BARBIERI 2002; BERBERINI 2005; ZUDDAS 2012.

² Since 2017, the Chair of Classical Archaeology at the University of Perugia, in synergy with the municipality of Cannara and the Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio dell'Umbria, has launched a research project aimed at identifying topographical elements essential for the overall understanding of urban organization and the enhancement of monumental realities previously come to light.

³ CIL XI 5168, now lost but reconstructed thanks to a nineteenth-century drawing, contained the mention of the ethnicity of the ancient Urvinate community.

⁴ For a detailed analysis of the characteristics of the Umbrian Valley see CAMERIERI, MANCONI 2010.

deduced from the toponyms of Fosso Fonte Salceto (to the West) and Contrada Fontebrava (to the East).

It is interesting to note how the location of the ancient Roman city differs from that of other nearby Roman centres of ancient foundation such as Assisi (*Asisium*), Spello (*Hispellum*), Bettona (*Vettona*) and Trevi (*Trebiae*): all these centres were built on a hill but at a lower altitude, all overlooking the lowland below, where other cities were located, like *Fulginium* and *Spoletium*⁵.

The site position offered several advantages, allowing the control of the entire road network that connected the pre-Roman Umbrian centres with transverse roads, at least until the realization of Via Flaminia, that crossed the valley creating a new artery, for an easier passage of the Roman consular armies heading towards northern Italy⁶.

According to the data collected so far, the Roman city seems to have reached its greatest economic, social, and cultural prosperity between the 1st and 2nd century AD, when the large and impressive work of monumentalization was accomplished.

As regards the possible causes that led the Roman municipium to its end, they are probably linked to the specific geomorphology of the territory; at some point, likely between the end of the 3rd and the beginning of the following century⁷, seismic events could have caused the exhausting of water so that the population had to move more to valley⁸. Nonetheless, a

⁵ MERCURELLI SALARI, ANNIBALI 1998, pp. 78-79.

⁶ MAURIZI 1979-1980, pp. 4-5.

⁷ On this subject see DE MEO 1985.

⁸ Basing on structural features of already known monuments and on materials recovered during the recent archaeological investigations, no phases after the end of the 3rd century AD is attested for the Roman town hall. More recent data are not in contrast with the

form of sporadic attendance of the site is proved by the remains of the 7th century AD church ('pieve') of Santa Maria, placed on the acropolar area, next to the ancient temple, and whose apse is set straight on the *cardo maximus*.⁹

E.C.

2. IMPORTED POTTERY: RELEVANT CONTEXTS AND FIRST DATA

The archaeological investigations led by University of Perugia between 2017 and 2019 have led to remarkable advances in knowledge about Roman occupation in Urvinum Hortense, also in regard to its first phases.

Since the previous campaigns did not rely on a modern scientific method based on stratigraphic criteria, it was necessary for us to isolate single contexts looking for specific data to define a secure dating of the earliest phases of occupation and development of the site. To this end, the preliminary analysis of imported ceramic material has certainly played a key role, although the number of useful pieces is quite limited at the current stage of research.

We identified some tranches through the site, included the area of the temple and the section where the thermal plant has been found; the excavation of these two contexts provided new data useful for a deeper understanding of the architectural development of archaeological evidence,

chronology of the latest inscription so far found, containing a dedication to the empress Magna Urbica dated 283-284 AD (CIL XI, 5168).

⁹ For an in-depth study of the birth and spatial evolution of the medieval sacred building see BINAZZI 1992 pp. 44-45; BARBIERI 2002, pp. 7-55 and BARBERINI 2005, pp. 7-42.

already identified during the excavations of the '30s, but now framed in a clearer chronological context¹⁰.

Considering the extent of the site and the likely increase in data as excavations progress, we will now consider a small group of ceramic material, which has played, at the present time, a fundamental function with regard to the first proposals for archaeological dating of some of the main and most significant structures in these two areas. This short analysis aims to represent a starting point for a future and more exhaustive typological study.

Therefore, in addition to the paper of Cecconi, Sciaramenti in this volume, we decided to examine the imported pottery that came to light during the excavations in the mentioned areas, because of their diagnostic value, privileging layers that are crucial to understand the historical evolution of each monument.

Due to both the study activities still in progress and the need for further data implementation, it is not yet possible to propose a general analysis of Urvinum's imported ceramics or a complete prospect of manufacturing and distribution centres, whose completion requires a more advanced phase of the study of Urvinum materials.

For now, we present some important results in order to put forward a proposal of archaeological dating of both stratigraphic contexts and architectural structures crucial to achieve the history of the site.

Given the above, it should still be considered the prospectus of distribution of the ceramic classes in the known part of the inhabited area,

¹⁰ Some information about the excavation activities of the early twentieth century is in BIZZOZZERO 1936. The author, as was customary at the time, kept a detailed daily diary of excavations.

based on data currently available, since it allows some important preliminary considerations. As can be seen in the graphic rendering (tab.1) in Urvinum Hortense there is a balanced relationship between the presence of local ceramics and imported ones, with a noticeable prevalence of the first ones.

Regarding the typological distribution of imported ceramics (tab.2), it is clear the predominance of amphoras and black varnished ceramic is well represented. Thin-walled and Italic sealed products are less common in terms of quantity, while African sealed products are sporadic¹¹, a fact that, if it will be confirmed by the further investigations underway, raises questions that should be taken into consideration.

G. G.

3. THE AREA OF THE TERMAL COMPLEX.

With regard to the thermal complex, the surveys made clear that this area has been affected by numerous interventions over time, which have given rise to different phases of occupation. No stratigraphic analysis of them had been proposed so far¹².

¹¹ With regard to imported ceramics, the present study refers to the study collections MENCHELLI, PAQUINUCCI 2006 and MATTEINI CHIARI 2002. In particular, on the sigillata from Urvinum Hortense, see CIPICIANI 2006 and CIPICIANI, DONNINI 2000; on the amphorae see DONNINI 2006.

¹² As mentioned, the baths were partially brought to light during the excavations of the early twentieth century. More recently, further exploratory essays and restoration work have been conducted by the Soprintendenza Archeologica dell'Umbria, and the results are contained in MANCONI 1987. In addition, a first definition regarding the function of the individual rooms identified is in BARBIERI 2002.

The excavation of 2019 included an assay within the peristyle (fig. 1), in correspondence with a semicircular brick lunette located at floor level, which can be interpreted as the sewer drainage arch functional to the bath complex.

Leaving aside the remarkable results achieved through this survey, we present a set of the imported diagnostic ceramic materials from those strata (respectively *nucleus* in cocciopesto and *statumen*, fig. 2), that make up the flooring of the columned impluvium, in order to provide useful elements for a first hypothesis of dating for a space that seems to be the main room of the entire thermal complex (figs. 3-6). In particular, there are a fragment of a dish in *sigillata italica* with a rim with slightly pointed almond profile, and a ring-shaped bottom of pertaining to hemispherical miniature cup.

On the basis of the aforementioned study of the first fragments, it is possible to suggest a general date for the context in question, that should be set at the first half of the 1st century AD, establishing, on an archaeological basis, one of the most significant phases of occupation of the entire area regarding to the monumental features.

Immediately to the east of the impluvium, where presumably the entrance to the original plant was located, the removal of the collapses offered the possibility of identifying a pavement in square terracotta slabs¹³. These were bedded on a preparatory layer composed mainly of mortar and small stones resting on a level of clayey earth. The pavement covered a gully consisting of a small wall in *opus testaceum* with a bottom paved with terracotta slabs and a roof made of stone and tiles (fig. 7). The canal, with a N-S trend, probably supplied the tub of the nearby frigidarium, the

¹³ Three of the plates are perfectly preserved, the others are fragmentary.

environment from which comes the mosaic with a nilotic subject now preserved at the Civic Museum of Cannara¹⁴.

The filling of the gully, a layer of quite friable dark-colored earth, provides incontrovertible evidence of the disuse of the water conduit in a phase datable between the middle of the 3rd century and the beginning of the 4th century AD, on the basis of the discovery of a Bonifay Type 25¹⁵ amphora rim in its C1 variant (= African Type IIC¹⁶) which attests to the importation of amphorae even in the final period of the municipality's life (fig. 8). The dating of the amphora fragment therefore reinforces the idea that the period of activity of the thermal complex, taking into account the available data, would begin in the proto-imperial age and would cease no more later than the beginning of the 4th century AD. During this period, the structure underwent structural and planimetric modifications that will only be possible to define precisely in relation to new stratigraphic investigations and an overall study.

E. C.

4. THE AREA OF THE TEMPLE

The objective of the excavation conducted in 2017 and 2018 on west of the temple was to undertake clean-up of the area in order to verify, if it were possible, the chronology of the most notable archaeological feature on the acropolis. This was of vital importance since the various proposals

¹⁴ A comparative study of the mosaic with a Nilotic subject is in SQUILLACE 2017.

¹⁵ BONIFAY 2004, pp. 114-115. This type is produced in the area of Nabeul, in present-day Tunisia, and was probably intended to contain *salsamenta*, salted fish.

¹⁶ PANELLA 1973, p. 586 ss.

considered the building, in its monumental and still visible vestiges, as the primordial seat of worship connected to the foundation of the city, but dated it just on the basis of general remarks on the birth and development of the ancient town.

Our investigation was possible only in the short northern portion outside the western wall of the sacred building, as all other sides were disrupted by earlier age investigations.

The excavation in foundation in search of dating materials began with the removal of the surface layer, related to the phase of abandonment of the temple, which has returned a large amount of heterogeneous material, both from the typological and chronological point of view, that brought to light a preparation of stone floor and pebbles of medium size, which therefore sealed the level of the foundations of the wall of the temple.

The removal of the aforementioned floor has brought to light a powerful filling level of about one meter thick, inside which half of a small stone altar, deliberately broken, has been found (fig. 9). A circular platform was found at the bottom of the thick fill, perfectly inscribed in the quadrangular perimeter of the upper room and finely made from slabs of calcarenitic stone, that had been cut, smoothed and put in place, then connected by strips of *cocciopesto* (fig. 10). The interesting monumental arrangement, specially made below the walking levels, is currently being studied.

What is interesting here, however, is the discovery, among the exceedingly rare ceramic material contained in the aforementioned filling, of a single diagnostic fragment, that is the portion of a background of a cup in ceramic overpainted, whose dating is to be assigned to the period between the 1st century BC and the 1st century AD (figs. 11-12). This dating

is encouraged by the discovery of a locally produced ceramic jug found in the same context¹⁷.

From the same stratigraphic unit come two further thin fragments of ceramic wall overpainted (fig. 13). The fragment does not presents included in an autopsy analysis; the dough is light pink (2.5 Y7 / 4) and the paint is red.

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¹⁷ See CECCONI, SCIARAMENTI in this issue.

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Fig. 1. Trench 6, excavation survey at the drainage arch of the sewer (ph. by Auth.).

Fig. 2. Trench 6, Section of the mosaic floor of the peristyle (el. by N. Cecconi).

Fig. 3. Trench 6, US 1717, n. inv. 19.5241-3.8992 (ph. and drawing by Auth.).

Description:

Sigillata italica; rim with slightly pointed almond profile, pertaining to Subform 20.3.2 (flat with vertical hem with simple band or with thin moldings), in ETLINGER *et alii* 1990, p. 86, taf. 18.

Datation:

late Augustan period

Production:

Italian workshops, including the Po region and Arezzo.

Fig. 4. Trench 6, US 1712, n. inv. 19.5241-3.8886 (ph. and drawing by Auth.).

Description:

Black-gloss; ring bottom pertaining to miniaturistic hemispherical cup of series and indeterminable species.

Datation:

Augustan age - First half of I sec. d.C. based on comparison to BERGAMINI 2011, p. 199, fig. 7.8.

Production:

Regional

Fig. 5. Trench 6, US 1717, n. inv. 19.5241-3.8991 (ph. and drawing by Auth.).

Description:

Thin walled, rim of nozzle with slightly flared walls pertaining to type I/166 (= Marabini LVI) in PUGLIESE CARRATELLI 1985, p. 275, tav. LXXXIX. 1.

Decoration:

with incisions obtained as a stick, the incisions are arranged vertically along the external wall of the shape. The decoration corresponds to the type 59 di PUGLIESE CARRATELLI 1985, p. 314, tav. CI, n. 5.

Datation:

Augustan-Tiberian age

Production:

Mediterranean area

Fig. 6. Trench 6, US 1717, n. inv. 19.5241-3.8991 (ph. and drawing by Auth.).

Description:

Thin walled, ring-shaped bottom pertaining to a cup with an almost cylindrical body and slightly flared walls of the type I/173 di PUGLIESE CARRATELLI 1985, tav. LXXXIX, 7.

Datation:

From the Augustan age to the second century A.D.

Production:

not identifiable.

Fig. 7. Trench 5. Detail of the channel and the flooring above (ph. by Auth.).

Fig. 8. Fragment of an amphora of the Bonifay Type 25 (el. by Auth.).

Fig. 9. Trench 1B-E, removal of the floor layer and partial exposure of the platform (ph. by Auth.).

Fig. 10. Trench 1B-E, fully exposed platform (ph. by Auth.).

Fig. 11. Fragment 2066 US 609, glazed pottery bottom (drawing by Auth.).

Fig. 12. Fragment 2066 US 609, glazed pottery bottom (ph. by Auth.).

Fig. 13. Fragments 4099-4100 US 609, glazed walls (ph by Auth.).

Tab. 1. Graph relating to the quantitative relationship between locally produced ceramics and imported ceramics.

Tab. 2. Graph relating to the quantitative relationship between the different ceramic classes.